

PLASTICIZATION OF CO-PRODUCTS FROM BIOETHANOL INDUSTRIES: POTENTIAL USES IN BIOCOMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

The depleting nature of petroleum resources and the increasing environmental pollution throughout the world have placed great emphasis on sustainable development. Also, the governments in many countries are supporting the usage of green products, and the reduction on petroleum carbon dependence because of the environmental benefits. Currently, the addition of cellulosic ethanol to transportation fuel is an attempt to reduce the use of fossil fuels. The main advantage of utilizing lignocellulosic materials for the production of ethanol is their abundance, renewability, sustainability, and carbon neutrality. In the production of cellulosic ethanol, soluble sugars are fermented through pretreatment of biomass followed by hydrolysis with a dilute acid or enzymes. As a result of this process, a considerable amount of solid residue (co-product) is produced which contains lignin, non-hydrolyzed carbohydrates, crystalline cellulose, and hemicellulose. Providing high value-added applications for these co-products will be economically beneficial and will help to sustain this industry in the long term. Production of the co-product is expected to reach about 225 million tons per year with the saturation of cellulosic ethanol production [1]. Recently, this co-product has found a wide range of potential in value-added applications such as plastics, carbon fibers, and fine chemicals. However, the major issue in the incorporation of this co-product, usually as a filler in various polymer matrices for the fabrication of

polymer composites, is its' poor compatibility with the polymer, resulting in products with inferior mechanical performance. Chemical modification is one of the most promising solutions for enhancing the compatibility between filler and matrix thereby increasing the usability of these co-products [2]. Studies on lignin grafting are very much concentrated. This is because of the inhibition of free radicals by the phenolic units in lignin, which can form quinoid resonance structures over the whole lignin molecule. Lignin has been grafted with methyl methacrylate, acrylonitrile, acrylic acid, vinyl acetate, maleic anhydride and styrene [3]. Maldure et al. [4] have investigated the esterified lignin/polypropylene blend. They observed a reduction in the percentage of crystallinity in modified lignin/PP blends. Microscopic studies revealed that the good dispersion and miscibility were achieved in modified lignin/PP blends. Setua and coworkers [5] studied modified lignin filled nitrile rubber. Kumaran and De [6] have also studied lignin filled styrene-butadiene rubber and natural rubber blended materials. Kharade and Kale [7] studied lignin filled polypropylene as well as low and high density polyethylene blends. They have observed better electrical resistance properties of those blends.

Graft co-polymerization of a hydrophobic monomer onto the co-product can enhance their compatibility with specific hydrophobic matrix polymer [8]. The graft co-polymerization of methyl methacrylate is one way to plasticize the co-product in order to improve its melt blending capabilities for composite applications. Jacob et al. [9] have studied plasticization of kraft lignin with methyl

methacrylate under aqueous medium. They have observed modified lignin hydrophobicity and surface area increased compared to the unmodified lignin. Satvinder et al. [10] have studied functionalization lignin with vinyl acetate. They have observed functionalized lignin shows more hydrophobic than lignin. Hence, the objective of present work was to investigate the grafting of the cellulosic ethanol co-product (which is a complex mixture of lignin, non hydrolyzed cellulose and hemicelluloses unlike pure lignin) with methyl methacrylate in order to improve compatibility with polymer matrices. In order to confirm the grafting, the graft co-polymerized bioethanol co-product was characterized by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTG), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and moisture absorption analysis.

2. Materials, Methods and Characterization

A solid residue of the enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated Poplar (EHL) was supplied by Mascoma, Canada and was used as received. EHL was directly obtained from the bioethanol industry without any further purification and thus it might have water soluble (sugar and oligosaccharides) molecules. Also, based on the companies technical data sheet information, EHL contains some alkali (sodium and potassium), phenolic acid and enzymes. EHL has a high content of lignin, the remaining content being non-hydrolyzed cellulose and hemicellulose. Methyl methacrylate (MMA) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. In order to remove the inhibitor from the monomer, the monomer was washed 2 to 3 times with 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, followed by washing with distilled water until the pH became neutral. Potassium persulfate and ammonium persulfate (redox initiator) were purchased from Caledon and Sigma Aldrich, respectively. Toluene was purchased from Fisher chemicals and used as received. EHL has 45 ± 2 wt% moisture content due to being frozen. Thus, it was dried in an oven at 105 °C for 12 h and grinded manually before modification.

2.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed by using a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 ATR-FTIR at ambient temperature. All the scans were performed from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . For each sample of the spectrum, 32 accumulated scans were produced and the transmittance was recorded as a function of wavenumbers. The data were recorded by using the OMNIC spectra software.

2.2 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Thermal stability of the EHL and MMA-g-EHL was measured by using a TA Q500 Instrument. The experiment was performed under inert N_2 atmosphere with controlled flow rate (60 ml min^{-1}). A small amount (5-10 mg) of sample was taken on a platinum pan and heated at 20 °C/min from room temperature to desired temperature. A graph of weight loss against temperature was obtained by the TA instrument software.

2.3 Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC)

The glass transition temperature of the samples was performed by a thermal analysis instrument Q 200. The experiment was performed under a nitrogen environment, which was injected with constant flow rate (50 ml/min). About 5-10 mg samples were precisely weighed in an aluminum pan and the sample pan was placed into the instrument. In order to remove the moisture, the samples were first heated from 0 to 80 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and held for 5 minutes. Samples were cooled down at a rate of 5 °C/min to 0 °C. Afterwards, samples were again heated to 200 °C with rate of heating 10 °C/min. A step transition (T_g) was obtained from the second heating cycle. DSC data analysis was done by thermal analysis instrument software.

2.4 X-Ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD)

XRD analysis was conducted under ambient condition on X-ray powder diffractometer using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation. Crystallinity index and percentage crystallinity were calculated by using their peak intensity.

2.5 Moisture Absorption Analysis

The moisture analysis of the sample was conducted in a desiccator with 95% relative humidity. The relative humidity was maintained using water at the bottom of the desiccator. Before starting the moisture analysis experiment the samples were dried in an oven at 105 °C for 12 h. Exactly 1g of oven dried samples were taken in a petri dish and placed in the desiccators. The moisture absorption was measured at different intervals. The moisture absorption test of the samples was performed until samples saturation was achieved.

2.6 Graft Copolymerization Reaction

Graft co-polymerization reaction was carried out in a round bottom flask equipped with a constant temperature oil bath. Methyl methacrylate (4 mL), EHL (4 g) and 40 mL of mildly acidified water were added slowly into the flask with constant stirring. To this mixture, potassium persulfate (9.24×10^{-2} m/l) and ammonium iron (II) sulfate hexahydrate (1.275×10^{-4} m/l) were introduced. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 12 h at 50 °C and the grafted EHL was filtered, dried and weighed. The formed poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) homopolymer was extracted through toluene soxhlet extraction for 48 h.

Scheme 1 Shows expected reaction mechanism of MMA grafting onto the EHL. The grafting yield was calculated by using following equation:

$$\text{Grafting yield (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where W_1 is weight of the EHL before grafting and W_2 is the weight of dried grafted EHL obtained after toluene soxhlet extraction. A maximum of 30% grafting yield was observed under these condition.

It is postulated that ferrous ammonium sulfate reacts with potassium persulfate to generate a SO_4^* radical. This SO_4^* radical is responsible for the chain propagation reaction and it helps in generating active sites on the polymer backbone where grafting can take place. In this case EHL hydroxyl groups are the most active sites for grafting with methyl methacrylate (MMA) monomer.

Reaction sites on the EHL backbone can be generated by the reaction between OH^* , SO_4^* and EHL [10]. The formation of hydroxyl (OH^*) and sulfate (SO_4^*) free radicals occurs by the reaction between the iron ion (Fe^{+2}) and potassium persulfate. The hydroxyl and sulfate free radicals induce the grafting reaction to generate the growing polymeric chains, which can react with the active sites of the EHL backbone to give the graft copolymers. Alternatively, the growing polymeric chains can favor the formation of homopolymer [10]. However, the removal of a hydrogen atom from main EHL backbone through is unlikely as the concentration of initiator is very small. In order to get better grafting yield, the ferric ions (Fe^{3+}) concentration in the reaction medium plays prominent role.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FTIR spectra of EHL and MMA-g-EHL are shown in the Fig.1. The EHL shows a broad distinctive hydroxyl peak at 3342 cm^{-1} . The peaks appeared at 2934 and 2838 cm^{-1} correspond to the C-H stretching of the alkane and alkene molecules, respectively. Peaks at 1597 and 1510 cm^{-1} correspond to aromatic ring vibration bands. The peak at 1326 cm^{-1} was mainly attributed to syringyl C-O stretching, which is present in the lignin moiety. At 1115 and 1030 cm^{-1} , the peaks were mainly attributed to the C-H stretching of polysaccharides. Few small peaks appeared at 831 and 618 cm^{-1} which account for lignin C-H stretching.

The MMA grafted EHL shows a drastic reduction in hydroxyl group intensity at 3400 cm^{-1} , which indicates that some of the hydroxyl groups are grafted with MMA. Similar observation was found in the MMA-g-kraft lignin. The peak at 1735 cm^{-1} corresponds to the carbonyl functionality. The structural difference between the EHL and MMA-g-EHL was confirmed by FTIR spectroscopy.

3.2 Thermogravimetric Analysis

Fig.2 shows TGA thermograms of EHL and MMA-g-EHL. The DTG curve of EHL clearly shows single step degradation at $359 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Whereas the MMA-g-

EHL exhibited two step degradation. The derivative peaks appeared at 206 °C and 415 °C. The MMA grafted chain may be degrading as a result of dehydration mechanism. Similar observations were made in the vinyl acetate grafted lignin compound [9]. The two step degradation mechanism of MMA-g-EHL may be occurring for two reasons; first, grafted MMA molecules can be considered an intermolecular steric hindrance on the EHL, which can cause a lower thermal stability. The second possible reason is that the grafted MMA molecules on the EHL may be smooth and cover the EHL backbone [11]. The grafted EHL's main decomposition temperature moves to higher temperature compared to EHL. It clearly shows that the MMA grafting on the EHL helps to increase the thermal stability of EHL. At 600 °C, char residue of EHL and MMA-g-EHL is 26.0% and 28.0%, respectively. There is no significant difference in char residue of EHL and MMA-g-EHL (Table 1).

3.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

DSC analysis was used to determine the glass transition temperature of EHL and MMA-g-EHL and the result is shown in Fig.3. Finding glass transition temperature of the lignin is complicated compared with synthetic polymers due to its structural irregularity. Fig.3 shows the DSC thermogram for EHL and MMA-g-EHL. The glass transition temperature of MMA-g-EHL clearly decreased compared to the EHL. It can be seen that MMA-g-EHL and EHL had T_g at 109 °C and 126 °C, respectively. The T_g reduction of MMA-g-EHL suggest that the MMA grafting had a plasticization effect on EHL [12]. The amorphous nature of the lignin is due to the complication in its structure irregularity. Therefore, lignin has no melting temperature (T_m) or crystallization temperature (T_c).

3.4 X-Ray Diffraction Analysis

The XRD graph of EHL and MMA-g-EHL is shown in Fig.4. XRD analysis was performed by an X-ray diffractometer. EHL contains different components such as hydrolyzed lignin and cellulose. These components have crystallinity differences based on

their chemical structure. Apparently, cellulose and lignin are crystalline and amorphous, respectively. Highly crystalline cellulose is difficult to hydrolyze by means of enzymatic hydrolysis and thus produces more high crystalline cellulose co-products. The cellulose crystallinity was traced by XRD analysis. EHL lignin has three peaks at $2\theta = 15$, 22.5 and 35 which correspond to the crystalline planes of cellulose 110, 110 and 200, respectively [12].

It is evident from Table 2 that unmodified EHL exhibits two characteristic peaks at $2\theta = 22.5$ and $2\theta = 15.0$ with intensities of 550 and 300 respectively. Percentage crystallinity (% Cr) of EHL was 64.70 and MMA-g-EHL 53.84. The higher and lower crystallinity of the cellulose peaks intensity appears at 22.5 and 15.0, respectively [13-14]. Crystalline index [15-16] and percentage crystallinity [17] were calculated as follows:

$$C.I = \frac{I_{22.5}}{I_{22.5} + I_{15}} * 100$$

$$\% Cr = \frac{I_{22.5} - I_{15}}{I_{22.5}}$$

The reduced crystallinity index of MMA-g-EHL indicated that the cellulose crystallinity was reduced in the grafted EHL, which was confirmed by the lower crystallinity index. This clearly indicates that cellulose crystal structure has a better arrangement in EHL compared to MMA-g-EHL. Moreover, the cellulose crystallinity was affected by the grafting reaction.

3.5 Moisture Absorption

Moisture absorption analysis of lignin is an important factor for some applications. Lignin is a complex hydrophobic natural polymer, despite the lignin free hydroxyl groups' ability to easily absorb moisture. In order to improve the hydrophobicity of lignin, the lignin free hydroxyl groups can be reacted with hydrophobic molecules [18]. From Fig.5, it was clearly observed that the EHL absorbed more moisture than MMA-g-EHL. Within one day, EHL and MMA-g-EHL absorbed 5.9 % and 3.8 %, respectively. This clearly indicates that the

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hydrophobic character of the MMA-g-EHL sample was higher than EHL. The grafted lignin absorbed some moisture because it may still have some free hydroxyl groups.

After 24 days of analysis, both samples were saturated. At saturation, EHL absorbed around 9.0 % moisture but the grafted EHL absorbed only 5.0 %. This result concluded that the hydrophobicity of grafted EHL reduced the moisture absorption. Similar results were reported in the literature. For instance, Wang et al. [19] observed a reduction in the moisture absorption of lignin by fictionalization with resin. Also, Satvinder et al. [10] reported that hydrophobicity of the vinyl acetate grafted lignin was increased compared to the lignin. Also, MMA-g-kraft lignin was showed more hydrophobic character than kraft lignin [9].

4. Conclusion

The MMA-g-EHL co-polymer was successfully synthesized. The FTIR spectrum showed a decreased intensity in the hydroxyl absorption and an increased as well as a sharp absorption peak for the carbonyl group absorption of the grafted product thus confirming the grafting. The experimental results showed that the grafting reaction allowed for modification of lignin functionality. The glass transition temperature of MMA-g-EHL decreases due to the grafted chain acting as a plasticizer, which was confirmed through DSC analysis. MMA-g-EHL showed an additional derivative peak compared to EHL. The additional peak (at 206 °C) mainly corresponds to the grafted chain of methyl methacrylate. The hydrophobicity of MMA-g-EHL increased compared to EHL, which was confirmed by moisture analysis. X-ray diffraction results confirmed that the cellulose crystallinity was reduced by the grafting reaction. Lignocellulosic bioethanol co-products are a non toxic, renewable, commercially available source for substituting petrochemical products. This study emphasized the future development and utilization of lignocellulosic bioethanol co-products for potential applications.

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Scheme 1. Expected reaction mechanism of MMA grafting onto the EHL including formation of homopolymer (PMMA).

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Table 1. Thermogravimetric analysis of the samples.

Samples	T _{onset} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T _{final} (°C)	Char at 600 °C (%)
EHL	244	359	378	26
MMA-g-EHL	155	206/415	443	28

Table 2 . XRD data of EHL and MMA-g-EHL

Samples	I _{22.5} (at 2θ scale)	I ₁₅ (at 2θ scale)	C.I	% Cr
EHL	550	300	0.45	64.70
MMA-g-EHL	350	300	0.14	53.84

Fig.2. TGA/DTG curve of EHL and MMA-g-EHL.

Fig.1. FT-IR spectra of EHL and MMA-g-EHL.

Fig.3. Differential scanning calorimetry of EHL and MMA-g-EHL

Fig.4. XRD results of EHL and MMA-g-EHL.

Fig. 5. Moisture absorption of EHL and MMA-g-EHL.